

Cg-Closed Sets And C-Normal Spaces

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduced a new class of sets called C-generalized closed (briefly Cg-closed) set which is a simultaneous generalization of C-closed and g-closed sets. First we investigated basic some properties of Cg-closed sets and then we obtained the relationship of Cg-closed sets with some other existing generalized closed sets. Moreover, we introduced the notion of C-Normal space by using C-closed sets, also we obtained some basic characterizations, properties and preservation theorems of C-normal spaces. Further, we also introduced some function related to Cg-open sets and investigated their properties with C-normal spaces.

Keyword:- C-closed set, F-closed sets, Cg-closed set, Fg-closed set, C-normal Space, almost Cg-closed function, almost Cg-continuous function etc.

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1. Introduction

Closed sets play a major role in the study of topological spaces. Generalized closed sets are a very useful research topic in topological spaces for many Topologists. In 1923, Tietze [8] first introduced the concept of normal spaces and studied their properties. In 1937, M. Stone [7] introduced the notion of regular open sets. In 1963, N. Levine [4] defined the concept of semi open sets and investigated their properties. In 1970, N. Levine [5] introduced the notion of generalized closed sets and studied the properties of g-closed sets in topological spaces. In 2002, K. Chandrasekhara Rao and K. Joseph [6] introduced the concept of s*g-closed sets in topological spaces. In 2023, Mesfer H. Alqahtani [1] introduced the concept of F-open and F-closed sets in topological spaces. In 2023, Mesfer H. Alqahtani [2] introduced the concept of C-open sets in topological spaces. In 2024, Hamant Kumar, B. S. Sharma and Anuj Kumar [3] introduced the concept of Fg-closed set which is the generalization of F-closed sets. They studied basic properties of these sets and examine the relationships between Fg-open and Fg-closed sets with other kinds of closed and open sets such as semi open, semi closed, w-open, w closed and g-open and g-closed sets etc.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout in this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let $f: X \rightarrow Y$ (or simply f) always denote a mapping from space X to space Y . Let B be a subset of a space X . The closure of B , interior of B and complement of B is denoted by $\text{cl}(B)$, $\text{int}(B)$ and B^c (or $X - B$) respectively.

Definition 2.1: A subset B of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be:

- (i) **regular open [7]** if $B = \text{int}(\text{cl}(B))$.
- (ii) **semi open [4]** if $B \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(B))$.
- (iii) **F-open [1]** if $\text{cl}(B) - B$ is finite set and B is open in X .
- (iv) **C-open [2]** if $\text{cl}(B) - B$ is countable set and B is open in X .

The complement of a regular open (resp. semi open, F-open and C-open set) set is called **regular closed** (resp. **semi closed**, **F-closed** and **C-closed**) set.

The intersection of all regular closed (resp. semi closed, F-closed and C-closed) sets containing B , is called **regular closure** (resp. **semi closure**, **F-closure** and **C-closure**) of B , and is denoted by **r-cl(B)** (resp. **s-cl(B)**, **F-cl(B)** and **C-cl(B)**). The union of all regular open (resp. semi open, F-open and C-open) sets contained in B , is called **regular interior** (resp. **semi interior**, **F-interior** and **C-interior**) of B , and is denoted by **r-int(B)** (resp. **s-int(B)**, **F-int(B)** and **C-int(B)**).

The collection of all regular open (resp. semi open, F-open and C-open) sets in X is denoted by **r-O(X)** (resp. **s-O(X)**, **F-O(X)** and **C-O(X)**). The collection of all regular closed (resp. semi closed, F-closed and C-closed) sets in X is denoted by **r-C(X)** (resp. **s-C(X)**, **F-C(X)** and **C-C(X)**).

Remark 2.2 From the above definitions the relationship among C-open sets and some other existing weaker and stronger forms of open sets are given as:

$$\text{F-open} \rightarrow \text{C-open} \rightarrow \text{open} \rightarrow \text{semi open}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible can be seen from the following examples:

Example 2.3 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $\{a, b\}$ is semi open set in X but not open set in X .

Example 2.4 Let $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{U})$ be the usual topological space then interval $[2, 5)$ is semi open in \mathbb{R} as $[2, 5) \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}([2, 5)))$ but not open in \mathbb{R} .

Example 2.5 Let $X = \mathbb{R}$ and \mathfrak{T} is the collection of all those subsets of \mathbb{R} which do not contain any irrational numbers together with \mathbb{R} then $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ be a topological space. Now the set of rational number \mathbb{Q} be an open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ but not a C-open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as: $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Q}) - \mathbb{Q} = \mathbb{R} - \mathbb{Q} = \mathbb{Q}^c$ (set of irrational numbers) which is an uncountable set.

Example 2.6 Let $X = \mathbb{R}$ and \mathfrak{T} is the collection of all those subsets of \mathbb{R} which contains a particular point 0 together with empty set \emptyset then $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ be a topological space. Now the set of integer \mathbb{Z} be an open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ but not C-open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as: $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Z}) - \mathbb{Z} = \mathbb{R} - \mathbb{Z}$ which is not a countable set.

Example 2.7 The set of natural numbers \mathbb{N} is a closed set of usual topological spaces $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{U})$ then $\mathbb{R} - \mathbb{N}$ is open set in \mathbb{R} , also C-open set in \mathbb{R} but not F-open set in \mathbb{R} as: $\text{cl}(\mathbb{R} - \mathbb{N}) - (\mathbb{R} - \mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{R} - (\mathbb{R} - \mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{N}$ which is countable set but not finite set.

Definition 2.8 A subset B of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be:

- (i) **g-closed [5]** if $\text{cl}(B) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (ii) **s*g-closed [6]** if $\text{cl}(B) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is semi-open.
- (iii) **Fg-closed [3]** if $\text{cl}(B) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is F-open.

3. Cg-closed sets

Definition 3.1 A subset B of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **Cg-closed** if $\text{cl}(B) \subset U$ whenever $B \subset U$ and U is C-open. The complement of the Cg-closed set is called Cg-open set. The collection of all Cg-open (resp. Cg-closed) sets is denoted by Cg-O(X) (resp. Cg-C(X)).

The intersection of all Cg-closed sets containing B , is called the Cg-closure of B and is denoted by $\text{Cg-cl}(B)$. The Cg-interior of B , denoted by $\text{Cg-int}(B)$ is defined to be the union of all Cg-open sets contained in B .

Theorem 3.2 Every s*g-closed set is Cg-closed set.

Proof: Let B be an s*g-closed set in X and let $B \subset U$ where U is C-open in X . Now every C-open set is semi open set and B is s*g-closed, so by the definition of s*g-closed set, $\text{cl}(B) \subset U$, hence B is Cg-closed set in X .

Theorem 3.3 Every g-closed set is Cg-closed set.

Proof: Let B be a g-closed set in X and let $B \subset U$ where U is C-open in X . Now every C-open set is open set and B is g-closed, so by the definition of g-closed set, $\text{cl}(B) \subset U$, hence B is Cg-closed set in X .

Theorem 3.4 Every Cg-closed set is Fg-closed set.

Proof: Let B be a Cg-closed set in X and let $B \subset U$ where U is F-open in X . Now every F-open set is C-open set and B is Cg-closed, so by the definition of Cg-closed set, $\text{cl}(B) \subset U$, hence it is clear that B is Fg-closed set in X .

Remark 3.5 We summarize the fundamental relationships between several types of generalized closed sets by the following implications:

closed \rightarrow s*g-closed \rightarrow g-closed \rightarrow Cg-closed \rightarrow Fg-closed

The converse of the above implication may not be true as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 3.6 Let for the set of real numbers \mathbb{R} , the collection of open sets $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{Q}^c, \mathbb{R}\}$ then $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ be a topological space. The set of integer \mathbb{Z} is not closed in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Z}) = \mathbb{Q}$, but \mathbb{Z} is an s*g-closed set as \mathbb{Q} is the smallest semi open set which contains \mathbb{Z} and $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Z}) = \mathbb{Q} \subset \mathbb{Q}$.

Example 3.7 For the set of real numbers \mathbb{R} , let the collection of open sets $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \mathbb{N}, \mathbb{R}\}$ (where \mathbb{N} is the set of natural number) then $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ be a topological space. Now the set of integer \mathbb{Z} is a g-closed in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as: \mathbb{R} is the smallest open set which contains \mathbb{Z} (because \mathbb{Z} is not open) and $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Z}) = \mathbb{R}$ also contained in \mathbb{R} . But \mathbb{Z} is not s*g-closed set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as: \mathbb{Z} be a semi open in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ (because $\mathbb{Z} \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(\mathbb{Z})) = \text{cl}(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{R}$) and $\mathbb{Z} \subset \mathbb{Z}$ but $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Z}) = \mathbb{R}$ is not subset of \mathbb{Z} .

Example 3.8 By example 2.5 the set of rational numbers \mathbb{Q} is a Cg-closed set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as set of real numbers \mathbb{R} is the smallest C-open set containing \mathbb{Q} (because \mathbb{Q} is not C-open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$) and $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Q}) = \mathbb{R} \subset \mathbb{R}$. But \mathbb{Q} is not a g-closed set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as \mathbb{Q} is open in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ also $\mathbb{Q} \subset \mathbb{Q}$ but $\text{cl}(\mathbb{Q}) = \mathbb{R}$ is not a subset of \mathbb{Q} .

Example 3.9 For topological spaces $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$, where $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \mathbb{N}, \mathbb{R}\}$. Now the set of natural numbers \mathbb{N} is a Cg-closed set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as the set of real numbers \mathbb{R} is the smallest C-open set containing \mathbb{N} (because \mathbb{N} is not C-open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as \mathbb{N} is open and $cl(\mathbb{N}) - \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{R} - \mathbb{N}$ which is an uncountable set) and $cl(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{R} \subset \mathbb{R}$. But \mathbb{N} is not a g-closed set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as \mathbb{N} is an open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ also $\mathbb{N} \subset \mathbb{N}$ but $cl(\mathbb{N}) = \mathbb{R}$ is not a subset of \mathbb{N} .

Example 3.10 For the topological space $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ where \mathbb{R} is the set of real numbers and \mathfrak{T} be the collection of open sets and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \mathbb{Q}^c, \mathbb{R}\}$, the set of irrational number \mathbb{Q}^c is a C-open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as \mathbb{Q}^c is open set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ and $cl(\mathbb{Q}^c) - \mathbb{Q}^c = \mathbb{R} - \mathbb{Q}^c = \mathbb{Q}$ which is a countable set. Now \mathbb{Q}^c is not a Cg-closed set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as \mathbb{Q}^c is C-open set and $\mathbb{Q}^c \subset \mathbb{Q}^c$ but $cl(\mathbb{Q}^c) = \mathbb{R}$ is not a subset of \mathbb{Q}^c , but \mathbb{Q}^c is an Fg-closed set in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$ as \mathbb{R} is the smallest F-open set which contains \mathbb{Q}^c (because \mathbb{Q}^c is not F-open in $(\mathbb{R}, \mathfrak{T})$) and $cl(\mathbb{Q}^c) = \mathbb{R} \subset \mathbb{R}$.

4. Properties of Cg-closed sets

Theorem 4.1: Union of two Cg-closed set is Cg-closed set.

Proof: Let J and K be two Cg-closed sets. Let U be a C-open set containing $J \cup K$. Now J is Cg-closed set then $cl(J) \subset U$ as $J \subset U$ and U is C-open set, also K is Cg-closed set then $cl(K) \subset U$ as $K \subset U$ and U is C-open set. Now $cl(J) \subset U$ and $cl(K) \subset U \Rightarrow cl(J) \cup cl(K) \subset U \Rightarrow cl(J \cup K) \subset U$ (because $cl(J \cup K) = cl(J) \cup cl(K)$). Hence $cl(J \cup K) \subset U$ whenever $J \cup K \subset U$ and U is C-open set. Hence $J \cup K$ is Cg-closed set.

In general finite union of Cg-closed sets is Cg-closed set.

Theorem 4.2: Intersection of two Cg-closed set is Cg-closed set.

Proof: Let J and K be two Cg-closed set. Now J is Cg-closed set if $cl(J) \subset U_1$ whenever $J \subset U_1$ and U_1 is C-open set, also K is Cg-closed set if $cl(K) \subset U_2$ whenever $K \subset U_2$ and U_2 is C-open set. Now $U_1 \cap U_2$ is C-open set as U_1 and U_2 are C-open sets, and $J \cap K \subset U_1 \cap U_2$ as $J \subset U_1$ and $K \subset U_2$. Now $cl(J) \subset U_1$ and $cl(K) \subset U_2 \Rightarrow cl(J) \cap cl(K) \subset U_1 \cap U_2 \Rightarrow cl(J \cap K) \subset U_1 \cap U_2$ (because $cl(J \cap K) \subset cl(J) \cap cl(K)$). Hence $cl(J \cap K) \subset U_1 \cap U_2$ whenever $J \cap K \subset U_1 \cap U_2$ and $U_1 \cap U_2$ is C-open set. Hence $J \cap K$ is Cg-closed set.

In general finite intersection of Cg-closed sets is Cg-closed set.

Theorem 4.3: Union of two Cg-open sets is Cg-open set.

Proof: Let G and H be two Cg-open subset of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Then $X - G$ and $X - H$ be two closed Cg-subset of X . Hence $(X - G) \cap (X - H)$ is Cg-closed subset of X by **Theorem 4.2** Now $(X - G) \cap (X - H) = X - (G \cup H)$ be Cg-closed set $\Rightarrow G \cup H$ is Cg-open set. Hence union of two Cg-open sets is Cg-open set.

In general finite union of Cg-open sets is Cg-open set.

Theorem 4.4: Intersection of two Cg-open sets is Cg-open set.

Proof: Let G and H be two Cg-open subset of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Then $X - G$ and $X - H$ be two Cg-closed subsets of X . Hence $(X - G) \cup (X - H)$ be the Cg-closed subset of X by **Theorem 4.1**. Now $(X - G) \cup (X - H) = X - (G \cap H)$ be Cg-closed set $\Rightarrow G \cap H$ is Cg-open set. Hence intersection of two Cg-open sets is Cg-open set.

In general finite intersection of Cg-open sets is Cg-open set.

Remark 4.5: Arbitrary union of Cg-closed sets is may not be Cg-closed set.

Example 4.6: For the set of natural number \mathbb{N} , \mathfrak{S} be the collection of all those subset of \mathbb{N} whose complement is finite together with the empty set, then \mathfrak{S} is cofinite topology for \mathbb{N} . Let $A_n = \{n+1\} \forall n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, \dots\}$ be the closed sets, hence Cg-closed subsets in the \mathbb{N} . Now let A be the countable union of A_n , i.e. $A = A_1 \cup A_2 \cup A_3 \cup A_4 \cup \dots = \{2, 3, 4, 5, \dots\} = \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$ which is not Cg-closed set as $A \subset \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$ and $\mathbb{N} - \{1\}$ is C-open set (as $\mathbb{N} - \{1\}$ is open set in \mathbb{N} , and $cl(\mathbb{N} - \{1\}) - (\mathbb{N} - \{1\}) = \mathbb{N} - (\mathbb{N} - \{1\}) = \text{singleton set } \{1\}$ which is countable) but $cl(A) = \mathbb{N}$ which is not subset of $\mathbb{N} - \{1\}$. Hence arbitrary union of Cg-closed sets is may not be Cg-closed set.

Remark 4.7: Arbitrary intersection of Cg-open sets is may not be Cg-open set.

Example 4.8: By **example 4.6**, $B_n = \mathbb{N} - \{n+1\} \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$ be the open set, hence Cg-open sets in \mathbb{N} . Now let B be the countable intersection of B_n , i. e. $B = B_1 \cap B_2 \cap B_3 \cap B_4 \dots = (\mathbb{N} - \{2\}) \cap (\mathbb{N} - \{3\}) \cap (\mathbb{N} - \{4\}) \cap (\mathbb{N} - \{5\}) \dots = \mathbb{N} - (\{2\} \cup \{3\} \cup \{4\} \cup \{5\} \dots) = \mathbb{N} - \{2, 3, 4, 5, \dots\} = \{1\}$ which is not a Cg-open set as $\mathbb{N} - \{1\}$ is not Cg-closed set by **Example 4.6**. Hence arbitrary intersection of Cg-open sets is may not be Cg-open set.

Definition 4.9: The intersection of all C-open subsets of a space X containing a set B is called the C-kernel of B and is denoted by $C\text{-ker}(B)$.

Lemma 4.10: A subset B of a space X is Cg-closed iff $cl(B) \subset C\text{-ker}(B)$.

Proof: Let B is a Cg-closed set in X . Then $cl(B) \subset U$ whenever $B \subset U$ and U is C-open in X . This implies $cl(B) \subset \bigcap \{U: B \subset U \text{ and } U \text{ is C-open in } X\}$ i. e. $cl(B) \subset C\text{-ker}(B)$.

Conversely, let $cl(B) \subset C\text{-ker}(B)$. This implies $cl(B) \subset \bigcap \{U: B \subset U \text{ and } U \text{ is C-open in } X\}$ i. e. $cl(B) \subset U$ whenever $B \subset U$ and U is C-open in X . This proves that B is Cg-closed.

5. C-NORMAL SPACES

Definition 5.1: A space X is said to be **C-normal** (resp. **normal** [8]) if for every pair of disjoint C-closed (resp. closed) sets J and K in X , there exist disjoint open sets G and H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$.

Remark 5.2: Every normal space is C-normal but not conversely.

Theorem 5.3 : For a topological space X , the following properties are equivalent:

- (1) X is C-normal;
- (2) for any disjoint $J, K \in C\text{-C}(X)$, there exist disjoint Cg-open sets G, H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$;
- (3) for any $J \in C\text{-C}(X)$ and any $H \in C\text{-O}(X)$ containing J , there exists a Cg-open set G of X such that $J \subset G \subset Cg\text{-cl}(G) \subset H$;
- (4) for any $J \in C\text{-C}(X)$ and any $H \in C\text{-O}(X)$ containing J , there exists an open set G of X such that $J \subset G \subset cl(G) \subset H$;
- (5) for any disjoint $J, K \in C\text{-C}(X)$, there exist disjoint regular open sets G, H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2): Since every open set is Cg-open, the proof is obvious.

(2) \Rightarrow (3): Let $J \in C-C(X)$ and H be any C -open set containing J . Then $J, X - H \in C-C(X)$ and $J \cap (X - H) = \phi$. By (2), there exist C_g -open sets G, F such that $J \subset G, X - H \subset F$ and $G \cap F = \phi$. Therefore, we have $J \subset G \subset (X - F) \subset H$. Since G is C_g -open and $X - F$ is C_g -closed, we obtain $J \subset G \subset C_g\text{-cl}(G) \subset (X - F) \subset H$.

(3) \Rightarrow (4): Let $J \in C-C(X)$ and $J \subset H \in C-O(X)$. By (3), there exists a C_g -open set G_0 of X such that $J \subset G_0 \subset C_g\text{-cl}(G_0) \subset H$. Since $C_g\text{-cl}(G_0)$ is C_g -closed and $H \in C-O(X)$, $\text{cl}(C_g\text{-cl}(G_0)) \subset H$. Put $\text{int}(G_0) = G$, then G is open and $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset H$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5): Let J, K be disjoint C -closed sets of X . Then $J \subset (X - K) \in C-O(X)$ and by (4) there exists an open set G_0 such that $J \subset G_0 \subset \text{cl}(G_0) \subset (X - K)$. Therefore, $H_0 = (X - \text{cl}(G_0))$ is an open set such that $J \subset G_0, K \subset H_0$ and $G_0 \cap H_0 = \phi$. Moreover, put $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(G_0))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(H_0))$, then G, H are regular open sets such that $J \subset G, K \subset H$ and $G \cap H = \phi$.

(5) \Rightarrow (1): This is obvious.

We get a characterization of normal spaces by using C_g -open sets.

Theorem 5.4: For a topological space X , the following properties are equivalent:

- (1) X is normal;
- (2) for any disjoint closed sets J and K , there exist disjoint C_g -open sets G and H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$;
- (3) for any closed set J and any open set H containing J , there exists a C_g -open set G of X such that $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset H$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2): This is obvious since every open set is C_g -open.

(2) \Rightarrow (3): Let J be a closed set and H be any open set containing J . Then J and $(X - H)$ are disjoint closed sets. There exist disjoint C_g -open sets G and F such that $J \subset G$ and $(X - H) \subset F$. Since $X - H$ is closed, we have $(X - H) \subset \text{int}(F)$ and $G \cap \text{int}(F) = \phi$. Therefore, we obtain $\text{cl}(G) \cap \text{int}(F) = \phi$ and hence $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset (X - \text{int}(F)) \subset H$.

(3) \Rightarrow (1): Let J, K be disjoint closed sets of X . Then $J \subset (X - K)$ and $(X - K)$ is open. By (3), there exists a C_g -open set F of X such that $J \subset F \subset \text{cl}(F) \subset (X - K)$. Since J is closed, we have $J \subset \text{int}(F)$. Put $G = \text{int}(F)$ and $H = (X - \text{cl}(F))$. Then G and H are disjoint open sets of X such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$. Hence, X is normal.

Lemma 5.5: A subset G of a space X is C_g -open if and only if $F \subset \text{int}(G)$ whenever $F \subset G$ and F is C -closed

Proof: let G be a C_g -open set then $X - G$ is C_g -closed set. Since $X - G$ is C_g -closed iff $\text{cl}(X - G) \subset X - G$ whenever $X - G \subset X - F$ and $X - F$ is C_g -open, this implies that $X - \text{int}(G) \subset X - F$ whenever $F \subset G$ and F is C_g -closed (because $\text{cl}(X - G) = X - \text{int}(G)$), i. e. $F \subset \text{int}(G)$ whenever $F \subset G$ and F is C_g -closed.

Theorem 5.6: For a space topological X , the following are equivalent:

- (1) X is C -normal.
- (2) For any disjoint C -closed sets J and K , there exist disjoint g -open sets G and H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$.

- (3) For any disjoint C-closed sets J and K , there exist disjoint Cg-open sets G and H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$.
- (4) For any C-closed set J and any C-open set H containing J , there exists a g-open set G of X such that $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset H$.
- (5) For any C-closed set J and any C-open set H containing J , there exists a Cg-open set G of X such that $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset H$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2): Let X be C-normal space. Let J, K be disjoint C-closed sets of X . By assumption, there exist disjoint open sets G, H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$. Since every open set is g-open, so G and H are g-open sets such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3): Let J and K be two disjoint C-closed sets. By assumption, there exist disjoint g-open sets G and H such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$. Since every g-open set is Cg-open, G and H are Cg-open sets such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$.

(3) \Rightarrow (4): Let J be any C-closed set and H be any C-open set containing J . By assumption, there exist disjoint Cg-open sets G and H_1 such that $J \subset G$ and $X - H \subset H_1$. By **Lemma 5.5**, we get $X - H \subset \text{int}(H_1)$ and $\text{cl}(G) \cap \text{int}(H_1) = \phi$. Hence $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset X - \text{int}(H_1) \subset H$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5): Let J be any C-closed set and H be any C-open set containing J . By assumption, there exist g-open set G of X such that $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset H$. Since, every g-open set is Cg-open, there exists Cg-open sets G of X such that $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset H$.

(5) \Rightarrow (1): Let J, K be any two disjoint C-closed sets of X . Then $J \subset X - K$ and $X - K$ is C-open. By assumption, there exists Cg-open set G_1 of X such that $J \subset G_1 \subset \text{cl}(G_1) \subset X - K$. Put $G = \text{int}(G_1)$, $H = X - \text{cl}(G_1)$. Then G and H are disjoint open sets of X such that $J \subset G$ and $K \subset H$.

Theorem 5.6: Let X be a C-normal space. Then a semi-regular subspace Y of X is also C-normal.

Proof: Let X be a C-normal space and Y be a semi-regular subspace of X . Let $J \in \text{C-C}(Y)$ and $H \in \text{C-O}(Y)$ containing J . Since Y is semi regular, so $J \in \text{C-C}(X)$ and $H \in \text{C-O}(X)$. Hence by **Theorem 5.3(4)**, there exists an open set G in X such that $J \subset G \subset \text{cl}_X(G) \subset H$. This gives $J \subset (G \cap Y) \subset \text{cl}_Y(G \cap Y) \subset H$, where $G \cap Y$ is open in Y and hence Y is C-normal.

6. FUNCTIONS AND C-NORMAL SPACES

Definition 6.1: A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be:

- (1) **almost Cg-continuous** if for any regular open set U of Y , $f^{-1}(U) \in \text{Cg-O}(X)$;
- (2) **almost Cg-closed** if for any regular closed set J of X , $f(J) \in \text{Cg-C}(Y)$.

Definition 6.2: A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be:

- (1) **C-irresolute (resp. C-continuous [2])** if for any C-open (resp. open) set U of Y , $f^{-1}(U)$ is C-open in X ;
- (2) **pre-C-closed (resp. C-closed [2])** if for any C-closed (resp. closed) set J of X , $f(J)$ is C-closed in Y .

Theorem 6.3: A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost Cg-closed surjection iff for each subset P of Y and each regular open set G containing $f^{-1}(P)$, there exists a Cg-open set H such that $P \subset H$ and $f^{-1}(H) \subset G$.

Proof: Necessity. Suppose that f is almost Cg-closed. Let P be a subset of Y and G be a regular open set of X containing $f^{-1}(P)$. Put $H = Y - f(X - G)$, then H is a Cg-open set of Y such that $P \subset H$ and $f^{-1}(H) \subset G$.

Sufficiency: Let J be any regular closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(J)) \subset (X - J)$ and $X - J$ is regular open. There exists a Cg-open set H of Y such that $(Y - f(J)) \subset H$ and $f^{-1}(H) \subset (X - J)$. Therefore, we have $f(J) \supset (Y - H)$ and $J \subset f^{-1}(Y - H)$. Hence, we obtain $f(J) = Y - H$ and $f(J)$ is Cg-closed in Y . Therefore f is almost Cg-closed.

Theorem 6.4: If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost Cg-closed C-irresolute (resp. C-continuous) surjection and X is C-normal, then Y is C-normal (resp. normal).

Proof: Let J and K be any disjoint C-closed (resp. closed) sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(J)$ and $f^{-1}(K)$ are disjoint C-closed sets of X . Since X is C-normal, there exist disjoint open sets G and H of X such that $f^{-1}(J) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(K) \subset H$. Put $G_1 = \text{int}(\text{cl}(G))$ and $H_1 = \text{int}(\text{cl}(H))$, then G_1 and H_1 are disjoint regular open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(J) \subset G_1$ and $f^{-1}(K) \subset H_1$. By **Theorem 6.3**, there exist Cg-open sets L and M of Y such that $J \subset L$, $K \subset M$, $f^{-1}(L) \subset G_1$ and $f^{-1}(M) \subset H_1$. Since G_1 and H_1 are disjoint, so L and M are also disjoint. It follows from **Theorem 5.3** (resp. **Theorem 5.4**) that Y is C-normal (resp. normal).

Theorem 6.5: If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a continuous almost Cg-closed surjection and X is a normal space, then Y is normal.

Proof: The proof is similar to that of **Theorem 6.4**.

Theorem 6.6: If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost Cg-continuous pre-C-closed (resp. C-closed) injection and Y is C-normal, then X is C-normal (resp. normal).

Proof: Let J and K be disjoint C-closed (resp. closed) sets of X . Since f is a pre-C-closed (resp. C-closed) injection, $f(J)$ and $f(K)$ are disjoint C-closed sets of Y . Since Y is C-normal, there exist disjoint open sets G and H such that $f(J) \subset G$ and $f(K) \subset H$. Now, put $G_1 = \text{int}(\text{cl}(G))$ and $H_1 = \text{int}(\text{cl}(H))$, then G_1 and H_1 are disjoint regular open sets such that $f(J) \subset G_1$ and $f(K) \subset H_1$. Since f is almost Cg-continuous, $f^{-1}(G_1)$ and $f^{-1}(H_1)$ are disjoint Cg-open sets such that $J \subset f^{-1}(G_1)$ and $K \subset f^{-1}(H_1)$. It follows from **Theorem 5.3** (resp. **Theorem 5.4**) that X is C-normal (resp. normal).

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